
Ventilation Noise and Learning

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SUMMARY

Existing Knowledge:

1. Ventilation in classrooms ensures good air quality, crucial for student health and cognition.
2. Indoor soundscapes influence speech perception, cognitive tasks, and overall acoustic comfort.
3. Noise from mechanical ventilation and open windows can disrupt learning and well-being.

New Insights:

1. Mechanical ventilation noise negatively affects speech perception, cognition, and comfort, especially at levels above 50 dBA.
2. Natural sounds, like water or bird songs, positively influence comfort and attention but may depend on sound levels.
3. Anthropogenic noise, such as traffic and construction sounds, generally impairs speech perception and cognitive performance.

Putting Research into Practice:

1. Design classrooms with quieter ventilation systems to meet acoustic standards (below 35 dBA) while maintaining air quality.
2. Incorporate natural sounds strategically in learning environments to improve comfort and cognitive function.
3. Enhance policies for classroom ventilation systems to balance acoustic and air quality requirements.

Keywords: classroom acoustics, ventilation noise, speech perception, cognitive performance, natural sounds, acoustic comfort

Reference:

Pellegatti, M., Torresin, S., Visentin, C., Babich, F., & Prodi, N. (2023). Indoor soundscape, speech perception, and cognition in classrooms: A systematic review on the effects of ventilation-related sounds on students. *Building and Environment*, 236, 110194. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.buildenv.2023.110194>

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